

On Frink's Type Metrization of Weighted Graphs

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Abstract

In this note, we present, test, and compare an explicit approach to generate a metric $d(x, y)$ between the vertices x and y of an affinity weighted undirected graph using the method of the metrization theorem of uniformities with countable bases.

Keywords: Weighted graphs, uniform spaces, and metrization.

• Introduction

One area of current interest in data analysis is the development of metrics in data sets. It goes without saying that the metrics constructed from a particular data collection should quantitatively represent the affinities between the various data pieces. The search for such metric structures on data sets is motivated by various factors. Specifically, appropriate metrics offer concepts of the vicinity of a given location that are not directly offered by the affinity a priori. More significant, though, is the fact that covering and partitioning may be done with metric spaces and that many of the characteristics of Euclidean spaces remain true.

a metric control that makes sense in every situation. Data structure metrization is important and has been mentioned in several of the seminal works on learning and data analysis, including [1, 2, 3, 4, and 5].

Diffusive metrics, developed by Coifman and Laffon [5], are arguably the most well-known metrization technique. The affinity matrix between the data is used to build a Laplace type operator. Then, the spectral analysis of this operator yields a diffusion kernel that provides a variety of metrics on the data set at various moments. A high dimensional space can be approximated by a low dimensional space by identifying its key properties according to the size of the eigenvalues. The metrization of general topological spaces is a well-known and ancient issue in pure mathematics. Specifically, when the uniform structure has a countable basis, the metrization of the topology generated on a set X by a uniformity on $X \times X$ was taken into consideration and solved in [6], see also [7] and [8]. As a result, if and only if the uniformity has a countable basis, a topology generated by a uniform structure is metrizable. Despite the fact that the results appear to have a qualitative nature, they are supported by a quantitative lemma by Frink that makes it possible to derive a metric from the affinity by passing through the

uniform structure that the affinity between the data points has created.

This quantitative lemma is originally used by Macias and Segovia ([9]) to demonstrate the equivalence of quasi-distances and powers of metrics. In [10], a Newton type potential form for a universal affinity kernel K on an abstract set X is obtained by providing sufficient conditions on K in terms of a natural metric on X . In general, [10] indicates that, under the assumption of quantitative transitivity, we have that $K(x, y) = \phi(d(x, y))$ for a quasi-convex decreasing function ϕ defined on the positive real numbers and some "metric" d .

In order to obtain a metric type function $d(x, y)$ between the vertices x and y associated with an affinity weighted network, we explicitly provide, test, and compare an approach in this note. In fact, the method produces a homogeneous family of metrics that collectively yield a sufficiently abundant family of balls.

The major result as a consequence of Frink's Lemma, as stated and proved in [8], is the focus of the second section of this note. The algorithm for the case of finite X is described in Section 3. We test and compare the technique in a few unique weighted graphs in Section 4.

Pseudometrization of Affinity Kernels and Weighted Undirected Graphs Through Frink's Lemma

The core theory requires no assumption on cardinality, even when the problem is motivated by the finite setting offered by weighted graphs. Therefore, we will assume in this section that X is a set and $K: X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a nonnegative function such that $K(x, y)$ is a measure of affinity between x and y for x and y in X .

A function $d: X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ such that (p-m.1) $d(x, x) = 0$ for every $x \in X$; (p-m.2) $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$, $x, y \in X$; and (p-m.3) $d(x, z) < d(x, y) + d(y, z)$ for every x, y , and $z \in X$ are examples of a pseudo-metric on the set X .

A metric that has $d(x, y) = 0$ only when $x = y$ is called a pseudo-metric.

Now, let us state Frink's Lemma as it is presented in Kelley's book [8], namely in

Chapter 6. It's necessary to make some notations to make more statements simpler. We indicate the diagonal of $X \times X$ with Δ . Stated otherwise, $\Delta = \{(x, x) : x \in X\}$. To represent the set $\{(x, y) \in X \times X : (y, x) \in U\}$, given a subset U of $X \times X$, we write U^{-1} . If $U = U^{-1}$, then we say that U is symmetric. The composition of $X \times X$, given two subsets U and V , is defined as $V \circ U = \{(x, z) \in X \times X : \text{there exist } y \in X \text{ such that } (x, y) \in U \text{ and } (y, z) \in V\}$.

Lemma 2.1: Given a set X , specify $\{U_m : m = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ as a series of subsets of $X \times X$ that have the given characteristics.

$\bigcap U_0 = X \times X$; $\bigcap U_n = U_{n-1}$ for each n ; $\bigcap \Delta \subset U_n$ for each n ; $U_{n+1} \subseteq U_n$ for each n .

Then, for each $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, there is a pseudo-metric d defined on X .

$$\{(x, y) \in X \times X : d(x, y) < 2^{-n}\} \subset U_{n+1}.$$

The control that the level sets of the pseudo-metric d have over the provided sequence $\{U_n : n = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ appears to be of a qualitative nature. However, this control becomes quantitative when the sequence U_n is itself given by level sets of some function K on $X \times X$, which enables the discovery of a natural notion of distance supplied by K .

In the continuation, we will utilise $V(n)$ to represent the composition $V \circ V \circ \dots \circ V$ n times for a given subset V of $X \times X$.

Now let us demonstrate that it is possible to create rising sequences $\{\lambda(k) : k = 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ such that, whenever $U_k = \{K > \lambda(k)\}$, $U_{k+1} \subseteq U_k$. This may be done under certain moderate conditions in K . Thus, the sequence U_k so obtained satisfies Lemma 2.1's primary criteria.

Lemma 2.2: Assume X is a set, and K is a nonnegative symmetric real function defined on $X \times X$ such that for every $x \in X$, $\sup_{y \in X} K(x, y) < \infty$. $0 < \Lambda < \infty = \sup\{\alpha > 0 : \{K > \alpha\}(m) = X \times X \text{ for any integer } m\} \leq \Lambda$.

Then, for every Λ such that $0 < \Lambda < \infty$, there exists a finite sequence $0 = \lambda(0) < \lambda(1) < \dots < \lambda(k) = \Lambda$ such that, for every $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$, $\{K > \lambda(i)\}(3) \subseteq \{K > \lambda(i-1)\}$. Furthermore, for each $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k$, $\Delta \subset \{K > \lambda(i)\}$.

Evidence. First, note that the set $A = \{\alpha > 0 : \{K > \alpha\}(m) = X \times X \text{ for a given integer } m\}$ is either the entire half line R^+ or an interval. The

monotonicity of K 's level sets implies this fact. Stated differently, if $\alpha \in A$ and $0 < \beta < \alpha$, then $\{K > \beta\} \supset \{K > \alpha\}$, meaning that $\{K > \beta\}(m) \supset \{K > \alpha\}(m) = X \times X$ and $\beta \in A$. However, we have that $\Delta \subset \{K > \alpha\}$ for any $\alpha \in A$. This is inferred from the kernel K 's attribute a). In actuality, if $K(x_0, x_0) < \alpha$ for some $x_0 \in X$, then $\sup_{y \in X} K(x_0, y) \leq \alpha$, and the point (x_0, x_0) would belong to $\{K > \alpha\}$ for no $m \in N$. However, since $\alpha \in A$, $\{K > \alpha\}(m) = X \times X \supset \{(x_0, x_0)\}$ for some m .

We will select $0 < \Lambda < \infty$. We know from the foregoing comments that $\Lambda \in A$ and $\Delta \subset \{K > \Lambda\}$. $m\Lambda = \min\{m \in N : \{K > \Lambda\}(m) = X \times X\}$ should be set. Stated otherwise, $\{K > (m\Lambda)\} = X \times X$, but $\{K > (m\Lambda - 1)\} \neq X \times X$. We can presume $m\Lambda \geq 3$. The set $A_1 = \{\alpha > 0 : \{K > \alpha\}(3) \subseteq \{K > \Lambda\}\}$ is now under consideration. The sequence we are searching for contains only two elements, $\lambda(0) = 0$ and $\lambda(1) = \Lambda$, if $A_1 = \emptyset$. Furthermore, it holds trivially that the required inclusion $\{K > \lambda(1)\}(3) \subseteq X \times X = \{K > \lambda(0)\}$. If $\Lambda_1 \in A_1$ and $\Lambda_1 > \sup A_1 - \epsilon$ for some fixed ϵ as small as required and positive ϵ , then $A_1 \neq \emptyset$. $A_2 = \{\alpha > 0 : \{K > \alpha\}(3) \subseteq \{K > \Lambda_1\}\}$ should now be set. We are done with $\lambda(0) = 0$, $\lambda(1) = \Lambda_1$, and $\lambda(2) = \Lambda$ if $A_2 = \emptyset$. The selection process can be repeated by selecting $\lambda_i \in A_i = \{\alpha > 0 : \{K > \alpha\}(3) \subseteq \{K > \lambda_{i-1}\}\}$ with $\lambda_i > \sup A_i - \epsilon$. Since the procedure finishes after at most the integer part of $m\Lambda/3 + 1$ iteration for $\{K > \Lambda\}(m\Lambda) = X \times X$, it yields a finite sequence of levels $\Lambda > \Lambda_1 > \Lambda_2 > \dots > \Lambda_k$. Taking $\lambda(i) = \Lambda_k - i$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, k$ yields the intended outcome.

It should be noted that selecting the sequence Γ_i in the above argument for discrete settings or continuous kernels K can be achieved by calculating the maximum of each A_i . Therefore, there's no need for the ϵ -approximation argument. We may declare and demonstrate the primary findings of this section using the two lemmas mentioned before.

Theorem 2.3. Let X represent a set. In Lemma 2.2, let K be a nonnegative symmetric function defined on $X \times X$ that satisfies a) and b). Then, as stated in Lemma 2.2, for every sequence $\lambda = \{\lambda(i) : i = 0, 1, \dots, k = k(\lambda)\}$, there is a pseudo-metric d_λ defined on X such that 1) $\{K > \lambda(i)\} \subseteq \{d_\lambda < 2^{-i}\} \subseteq \{K > \lambda(i-1)\}$ for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$; 2) the function $\lambda \delta = 2^{-\lambda-1} \circ K$, where $\lambda-1$ is the inverse of any increasing extension of $\lambda(i)$ to the whole interval $[0, k(\lambda)]$, is equivalent to the pseudo-metric d_λ with constants that are uniform in λ . Specifically, $d(x, y) \leq 2d_\lambda(x, y) < 4\psi_\lambda(x, y)$.

Evidence. The sequence $U_i = \{K > \lambda(i)\}$ from Lemma 2.2 fulfils Lemma 2.1's i) through iv). Therefore, 1) holds for any pseudo-metric $d\lambda$ defined on X . To demonstrate 2), assume that $(x, y) \in X \times X$ and that $d\lambda(x, y) > 0$. Hence, we get $2^{-(i+1)} \leq d\lambda(x, y) < 2^{-i}$ for some $i = 0, 1, \dots, k(\lambda)$.

$K(x, y) > \lambda(i)$ as seen by the second inclusion in 1) and the condition $d\lambda(x, y) < 2^{-i}$. $K(x, y) = \lambda(i+1)$ is demonstrated by the inequality $2^{-(i+1)} d\lambda(x, y)$ and the first inclusion in 1. Since λ represents the inverse function of each strictly increasing extension of the sequence $\lambda(i)$ for $i = 0, \dots, k$ to the interval $[0, k]$, we can write: $2^{-(i+1)} \leq d\lambda(x, y) < 2^{-i}$, and $i - 1 < \lambda^{-1}(K(x, y)) \leq i + 1$.

It may be easily deduced from these inequalities that $\delta\lambda = 2^{-\lambda^{-1} \circ K}$ is equal to d . Actually,

$$d(x, y) 2^{(\lambda^{-1} \circ K)(x, y)} \leq 2^{-2i+1} = 2^{-\lambda^{-1} \circ K(x, y)}$$

Let us note that, regardless of the kernel K or the sequence λ , which fulfil Lemma 2.2, the function $\delta\lambda$ in the preceding conclusion satisfies a triangle type inequality with triangular constant equal to 8. For every x, y , and $z \in X$, $\delta\lambda(x, z) \leq 4d\lambda(x, z) \leq 4(d\lambda(x, y) + d\lambda(y, z)) < 8(\delta\lambda(x, y) + \delta\lambda(y, z))$.

λ

Considering the expansion of λ to generate the function λ^{-1} , which is required to provide the quasi-metric δ explicitly, we can note that two extreme scenarios can be provided. Let $\lambda^{-1} :$

• **The Algorithm for the Explicit Computation of the Sequences λ . The Finite Case**

- We examine the scenario where $X = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ for a large integer n in this section. It is possible to think of the kernel K defined on $X \times X$ as a $n \times n$ symmetric matrix with positive entries K_{ij} . Since $\Lambda^\infty \geq \min K_{ij} > 0$, hypothesis b) in Lemma 2.2 holds trivially because each K_{ij} is positive. Alternatively, if $K_{ii} = \sup_j K_{ij}$, then Lemma 2.2's hypothesis a) is true.

$[0, \lambda(k)] \rightarrow [0, k]$ actually be defined as follows: $\lambda^{-1}(t) = i$ for $\lambda(i-1) < t \leq \lambda(i)$ and $i = 1, \dots, k$. Furthermore, $\lambda^{-1}(0) = 0$. A lower case $\lambda^{-1} : [0, \lambda(k)] \rightarrow [0, k-1]$ is another potential λ^{-1} , and it is represented by $\lambda^{-1}(t) = i-1$ for $\lambda(i-1) < t \leq \lambda(i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, k$.

It is also important to note that the scaling factor related to the selection of Λ in Lemma 2.2 is not reflected in Frink's metric, and consequently, in $\delta\lambda$. The reason for this is that only values between zero and one are accepted by Frink's measure, $d\lambda$. Because $\delta\lambda$ is equal to $d\lambda$, our quasi-metric $\delta\lambda$ is likewise bounded.

Additionally, a family of $\delta\lambda$ balls that are directly defined as level sets of the affinity kernel K are contained in the sequence $\lambda(i)$.

r Proposition 2.1 states that the open λ ball with radius r and centre at x in X is given by for $0 < r < 1$.

$y \in X: K(x, y) > \lambda(\log_2 1/r)$ is the result of $B_{\delta\lambda}(x, r)$.

Evidence. The condition $\delta\lambda(x, y) < r$, which determines $B_{\delta\lambda}$, is similar to $K(x, y) > \lambda(\log_2 1/r)$.

(x, r) .

$r \lambda$

It is important to note that K alone will determine how the sequence $\lambda(i)$ is really constructed. Therefore, K is the only one who can supply the $\delta\lambda$ balls.

- To build the sequences λ and $\delta\lambda$ related to this matrix K , we will have to deal with the diagonal's neighbourhood composition in the algorithm.
- Let $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}^2 = X \times X$ consist of two subsets, U and V . Then, for some $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, $V \subseteq U = \{(i, k): (i, j) \in U \text{ and } (j, k) \in V, \text{ as before.}$
- Section 3.1. Set $AU = (a_{ij}(U))$ to represent the $n \times n$ rest matrix for a given $U \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, which is defined by $a_{ij}(U) = 1$ if $(i, j) \in U$ and $a_{ij}(U) = 0$ otherwise. The non-vanishing entries of the product matrix $AU AV$ thus produce the set $V \subseteq U$. Specifically

- `zeros((n))` for `i` in range `(n-1)`: `aux=np`
- Comparing the inner values of the major diagonals and `aux[i]` equals `min(K[i, i], K[i, i+1])`.
- `##` Examine the residual values in the primary diagonals `aux[n-1]=K[n-1,n-1] lambda 0=min` (auxiliary)
-
-
-
- The matrix `A` is defined as follows: `A=np.zeros((n, n))`
-
- When `i` and `j` are in the same range `(n)`, their formulas are as follows: `if K[i, j]>=lambda 0: A[i, j]=1`.
-
- `##` Calculate `B=(A.dot(A)).dot(A) B=A^3`
-
- `##` Calculate `Bpos`
- `Zeros((n, n))` for `i` in range `(n)`: for `j` in range `(n)`: `if B[i, j]>=1: Bpos[i, j]=1 Bpos=np`
-
- `##` Calculate `C = K * Bpos ##` Determine the lowest of the positive values of `C` `auC=np.max(K)` for `i` in range `(n)`: regarding `j` in range `(n)`: When `C[i, j] >0`, then `auxC=min` (`auxC, C[i, j]`) `lambda 1` equals `auxC`
-
- `##` Indices `##` Attributes
-
- `zeros((n)) lambda i [0] = lambda 0 lambda i [1] = lambda 1 lambda i=np`
-
- `zeros((n, n)) = A i=np`
- `l = A i [0, :, :]`
-
- `•i=np.zeros((n, n)) B i [0, :, :] =B`
-
- `Zeros((n, n)) Bpos i=np`
- `Bpos = Bpos i [0, :, :]`
-
- `•i=np.zeros((n, n)) C i [0, :, :] =C`
-
- `##` When `h` equals one
-
-
- `lambda i [h]>Kmin` while: `##` Define matrix `A` as follows for `i` in range `(n)`: `if K[i, j]>` for `j` in range `(n)`. `i [h] = lambda i: A i [h, i, j]=1`
-
- `##` Calculate `l [h, :, :] = ( A i [h, :, :] ) B=A^3. A i [h, :, :]) ) dot. ( A i [h, :, :] ) dot`
-
- `##` `Bpos` for `i` in range `(n)`: for `j` in range `(n)`: `if B i [h, i, j] >=1: Bpos i [h, i, j]=1`
-
- `##` Determine `C C i [h, :, :] Bpos i =K* [h, :, :]`
- `##` Determine the minimum of the positive values of `C` with the formula `auC=np.max(K)` for `i` in range `(n)`: for `j` in range `(n)`: `if C i [h, i, j] >0: auC=min` (`auxC, C i [h, i, j]`) `[h+1] lambda i = auxC h+=1`
-
- `##` Conclude whilst
-
- `##` Moving `lambda` Around
- `lambda l` equals `lambda l [0: h+1] [ : - 1 ] lambda i= lambda i`
- `##` Reversing the function of `lambda` `func inv (t, lambda ) def lambda :`
- If `t` is less than zero, print (' `t` must to be less than or equal to the minimum value of `lambda`')
- For each `kk` in the range `(len ( lambda ) - 1 )`, `if lambda [ kk]<=t\lambda [ kk + 1 ]: inv=kk+1`
- For any `t>=lambda [len ( lambda ) - 1 ]`, the formula is `inv=len ( lambda )` return `inv`.
-
- `##` Calculate the matrix `(nodo1, nodo2)` `def distfrinkinv:`
- `Finv =2*(-lambda func inv (K[ nodo1, nodo2 ], lambda i)) Dist Finv`
- return to this `Finv`
-
-
- `distarray Finv=np.zeros((n, n))` for `v` in range `(n)`: for `w` in range `(n)`: `distarray Finv [v, w]=distfrinkinv (v, w)`
-
- Create the graph starting by using `K G = nx. Graph ()` from numpy matrix `(np. matrix (K))` to `G = nx`

-
- Plot the graph layout as follows: `## nx.spr in g layout (G)`
-
- `figure (plt)`
- `plt.title(' Graph') nodecolor=np. ones ( n) nx. draw (G, layout, nodecolor=no de color, with labels=False ) nx. draw ne two r labels (G, layout, font size=12, fo nt family=' sans-serif') plt. show ()`
-
- `## Sketching balls centred at i for k in range (n): for v in range (h+1): if dist array F [ i ] [ k ] > lambda i [ v ]: nodecolor [ k]=h-v nodecolor [ i]=h+1`

Fig. 1. Graph

Let us also point out that in the following graphs, the numerical label of each vertex is assigned according to the order of the rows in the affinity matrix, but a priori has nothing to do with distance or affinity.

Fig. 1 labels with the integers 0, 1, . . . , 59 the 60 vertices of our graph.

Test and Comparison with the Diffusive Metric for Newtonian Type Affinities

The results in [10] suggest testing the algorithm on affinities defined as discretizations of Newtonian type potentials of the form

$$K(x, y) = \frac{1}{|x - y|^\alpha}$$

for α positive. Once a discretization of K_α is given we may run our algorithm and also the well known diffusion metric introduced in [5]. See also [11]. Let us recall that the diffusive metric at time $t > 0$ is given by

where $x^l, v_l, l = 1, \dots, L$ are the eigenvectors and the eigenvalues of the Laplace operator on the graph with affinity given by the metric K_{ij} .

We shall only write down the comparison of the families of δ_λ -balls, d_t -balls and Euclidean balls for a couple of values of the radio, when we consider the discretization

It is worthy pointing out at here that the choice of 60 points of discretization is only taken for the sake of getting better images for the graphs. In particular for the visibility of some edges.

(D) Y, G, 0.11, T, 0.135, L, 0.31, P, (F) Y, 0.0169492, G, 0.037037, T, 0.111111,

0.404327

L, 0.333333, P, 1

(E) Y, G, 1, T, 3, L, 27, P, 59

Fig. 2. Center at 50

Now, for each of the three metrics—the Euclidean metric (E), the diffusive metric (D) with $t = 0.005$, and the Frink's metric—we will depict several balls with centres at 25 and 50. Since K is constructed in terms of the Euclidean (E), it is imperative to compare (D) and (F) with (E). Again, let us state that the form of the balls is what interests us, not the specific radii at which they are obtained. In this instance, where the Euclidean metric is unbounded, this point is very evident. Nevertheless, we will include the radii for each ball in each measure that are depicted. Actually, the annuli between two successive balls are depicted in various colours in the following photos. We utilise green for the first annulus, turquoise for the second, lavender for the third, and purple for the final annulus, with yellow serving as the centre.

The colours are denoted in Figs. 2 and 3 by the capital letters Y, G, T, L, and P. The inner and outer radii of each annulus are indicated by the letter and number sequences.

It is important to note that the raddi sequence for (D) has been selected so that the dt balls approach Euclidean balls as closely as feasible. The metrization approach (F) described here appears to recreate, at least for this basic case of a kernel defined by a metric, the exact forms of the balls associated with the metric defining the kernel. One could argue that Frink's construction's exponential nature only yields a small number of the graph's balls. However, we know from the very proof of our primary result that we can obtain a profuse diversity of sequences $\lambda(i)$ by just modifying the initial parameter $\Lambda < \Lambda\infty$. The use of our affinity matrix K's main three diagonals is another somewhat discretionary algorithmic step. Restarting with the primary five diagonals will yield an additional family of annuli and F-balls.

(D) Y, G, 0.13, T, 0.17, L, 0.212, P, 0.404327

(F) Y, 0.0169492

L, 0.333333, P, 1

(E) Y, G, 1, T, 3, L, 27, P, 59

Fig. 3. Center at 25

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